

AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PADDY CULTIVATION IN KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Paddy cultivation is the most important and extensively grown food crop in the world. It is basically food for more than 60 per cent of the world population. Majority of the Asian people consumed and produced in paddy. India has the largest area under paddy cultivation in the world after China. The present study identify with different Paddy forming systems in the study area, to find out problem of organic paddy production and marketing. The present study it is based on primary and secondary source of information.

Keywords: Organic Farming, Growth, Fertilizers.

INTRODUCTION

Paddy is the most important and extensively grown food crop in the world. It is staple food for more than 60 percent of the world population. Paddy is mainly produced and consumed in the Asian region. India has the largest area under paddy in the world and ranks second in the production after China country has also emerged as a major rice consumer.

A paddy field is a flooded parcel of arable land used for growing paddy ad other semi aquatic crops. Paddy fields are a typical feature of rice farming in east, south and Southwest Asia. Paddies can be built into steep hillsides as terraces and adjacent to depressed or steeply sloped features such as rivers and marshes. Flooded paddies provide an ideal environment for paddy cultivation and discourage the growth of many weeds. The water buffalo is one of the most important working animals adopted for life in wetlands and is utilized extensively in paddy field farming.

Importance of Paddy Cultivation: Rice has shaped the culture, diets and economic of thousands of millions of peoples. For more than half of the humanity” rice is life” considering its importance position, the united nation designated year 2004 as the “international year of rice, importance of rice are as follows:

- Rice is an important staple food crop for more than 60 percent of the world people. In 2008, more than 430 million metric tons of rice were consumed worldwide, according to the USDA.
- Ready to eat products eg. Popped and puffed rice, instant as rice flakes, conned rice and fermented products are produced.

- Rice straw is used as cattle feed, used for thatching roof and in cottage industry for preparation of hats, mats, ropes, sound absorbing, straw board and used as litter material.
- Rice husk is used as animal feed, for paper making and as fuel source.
- Rice bran is used in cattle and poultry feed, defatted bran, which is protein, can be used in the preparation of biscuits and as cattle feed.
- Rice bran oil is used in soap industry. Refined oil can be used as a coating medium like cotton seed oil/ corn oil. Rice bran wax, a byproduct of rice bran oil is used in industries.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A very brief review of studies on the subject has been made here under;

P.M. Thamas (1991) in his research article entitled “Performance of the agriculture sector in India” argued that even though, the total land area in India. The country has 162 million hectares of arable land in the world. The performance of the Indian agriculture sector is a crucial determinant of the over producing sectors is a crucial linkages to other producing sectors is a crucial determinant of the overall development of the economy. The share of agriculture income in the SDP of the country, rate of capital information in the agriculture sector changes in land use pattern, changes in raring pattern and production and yield of major crops are taken as the indicators of performance some of the major factors that determine the performance of this sector like rainfall and irrigation and irrigation crop-wise coverage of high yield variety seeds, use of fertilizes and size of land holdings are discussed in the second section.

Mohandas and Thomas (1997) in their research paper entitled Economics of Production in Kultanad Area of Kerala, identified the cost of cultivation of paddy of state was 13,108,05 marginal farmers R.S 13,309 72 for small farmers and R.S 13,858,13 for class II rich accounted to 24.19 percent and 22.38 percent respectively. The study found that item of highest for marginal farmers, the net returns and input output ratio was also found to be highest in marginal farmers followed by small farmers and large farmers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following two are the objectives of the present paper.

- To identify different Paddy forming systems in the study area.
- To find out problem of organic paddy production and marketing.
- To Study the problems of Paddy cultivation in Karnataka

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table: 1 - Gender-Wise Classification of Respondents

Sl. No	Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage
1.	Male	24	80
2.	Female	06	20
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, December 2018

The above table shows that the gender wise classification of respondents. Among 30 sample respondents interviewed, 80 per cent of the respondents are males and the remaining 20 per

cent of the respondents are females. This shows the majority of the respondents in the study area are males.

Table: 2 - Age of Respondents

Sl. No	Age	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	20-30	01	3.3
2	31-40	09	30
3	45-50	11	36.7
4	50 and above	09	30
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table indicates that the age-wise classification of respondents. Out of 30 respondents interviewed, 3.3 per cent of the respondents are in between the age group of 20-30, 30 per cent of the respondents are between 31-40, 36.7 per cent of are between the age group of 45-50 years and the remaining 30 per cent of the respondents are in the age group of above 50 years. This indicates that majority of the respondents are in the age group of between 40 50 years.

Table: 3 - Education Levels of Respondents

Sl. No	Education	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Illiterates	11	36.66
2	Primary	11	36.66
3	High school	06	20.0
4	Graduate	02	6.7
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table reveals the education level of the respondents. Out of 30 respondents interviewed, 36.66 per cent of the respondents are illiterates, 36.66 per cent of the respondents are having education level up to primary, 20 per cent of the respondents are having education level up to high school and the remaining 6.7 per cent of the respondents are having education up to primary graduation level. This shows that majority of the respondents in the study area are having education level up to primary level.

Table: 4 - Occupations and Annual Income of the Respondents

Sl. No	Occupation	No. of respondents	Annual income	Percentage
1	Farmers	25 (83.33%)	10000-50000	08 (26.66%)
2	Self-employees	04 (13.34%)	50000-100000	07 (23.34%)
3	Employees	00 (00.00%)	100000-150000	07 (23.34%)
4	Others	01 (03.37%)	150000-200000	08 (26.66%)
	Total	30 (100.00%)	Total	30 (100.00%)

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table depicts the occupation of the sample respondents. Out of 30 respondents interviewed, 83.33 per cent of the respondents are farmers, 13.34 per cent of the respondents are self- employees and the remaining 3.37 per cent of the respondents are having other type of occupations; ,

26.66 per cent of the respondents' opinion annual income is between 10000 to 50000, 23.34 per cent of the respondents' opinion annual income is between 50000 to 100000, 23.34 per cent of the respondents' annual income is between 100000 to 150000 and the remaining 26.66 per cent of the respondents annual income is between 150000 to 200000.

Table: 5 - Use of Fertilizers and Method in Paddy Cultivation

Sl. No	Fertilizers	No. of respondents %	Method	No. of respondents %
1	Organic	07 (23.33%)	Modern	17 (56.66%)
2	Inorganic	23 (76.67%)	Traditional	13 (43.34%)
	Total	30 (100.00%)	Total	100 (100.00%)

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table shows the use of fertilizers in paddy cultivation of the sample respondents. Out of 30 respondents interviewed, 23.33 per cent of the respondents utilize organic fertilizers and the remaining 76.60 per cent of the respondents are using inorganic fertilizers for their cultivation; 56.66 per cent of the respondents are following modern methods for paddy cultivation and the remaining

43.34 per cent of the respondents are following tradition methods for paddy cultivation.

Table: 6 - Sources of Water of the Respondents

Sl. No	Sources of water	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Rainfed	15	50
2	Borewell	13	43
3	Canal	00	00.0
4	Other sources	02	07
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table shows that the sources of water of the sample respondents. Among 30 interviewed respondents, 50 per cent of the respondents are depending on rain for their cultivation, 43 per cent of the respondents are depend on bore wells, and the remaining 7 per cent of the respondents depending on other forms of sources of water for paddy cultivation. This shows that majority of the respondents in the study area are depending on rainfed water sources for cultivating paddy.

Table: 7 - Type of Soil and Type of Land of the Respondents

Sl. No	Type of soil	No. of respondents	Type of land	Percentage
1	Red	25 (83.00%)	Dry land	03 (10.00%)
2	Sandy	02 (07.00%)	Irrigated land	09 (30.00%)
3	Black	03 (10.00%)	Rain dependent	18 (60.00%)
4	Other types	00 (00.00%)	Other land	00 (00.00%)
	Total	30 (100.00%)	Total	30 (100.00%)

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The table above shows the type of soil and type land of the sample respondents. Among 30 interviewed respondents, 83 per cent of the respondents opinion lands are red soil lands, 7 per cent of the respondents' opinion lands are sandy soil lands and 10 per cent of the respondents' opinion lands are having other types of soils in their land; 10 per cent of the respondents are

having dry lands, 30 per cent of the respondents are having irrigated land and the remaining 60 per cent of the respondents are having rain dependent lands.

Table: 8 - Varieties of Paddy of the Respondents

Sl. No	Varieties of paddy	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Local	17	56.6
2	High yield	13	43.4
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table shows the varieties of paddy of the respondents. Among 30 interviewed respondents, 56.6 per cent of the respondents grow local variety of paddy and the remaining 43.4 per cent of the respondents grow high yield variety of paddy. The table shows that majority of the respondents are growing local variety of paddy.

Table: 9 - Sources of Credit of the Respondents

Sl. No	Sources of credit	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Non institutional	07	24
2	Commercial banks	00	00
3	Cooperative banks	19	63.4
4	Regional banks	05	16.6
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table shows the sources of credit facilities of the respondents. Out of 30 respondents interviewed, 24 per cent of the respondents are getting credit from non-institutions, 63.4 per cent of the respondents are getting credit from cooperative banks and the remaining 16.6 per cent of the respondents are getting loan from the regional banks. It can be clear from the table that majority of the respondents that is 63.4 per cent of the respondents are getting loan from cooperative banks.

Table: 10 - Nature of the Marketing and landholding of the Respondents

Sl. No	Nature of the marketing	No. of respondents %	Landholding	No. of respondents %
1	Local	09 (30%)	Small farmers	17(56%)
2	APMC	17(56.70%)	Medium farmers	13(44%)
3	Commission agents	04(13.30%)	Large farmers	00(00%)
	Total	30 (100%)	Total	30(100%)

Source: Field Survey, December 2018.

The above table shows the nature of marketing the product of the respondents. Among 30 respondents interviewed, 30 per cent of the respondent's opinion local markets, 56.7 per cent of the respondents opinion APMC markets and 13.3 per cent of the respondents sell their produce through commission agents; 56 per cent of the respondents are opinion small farmers and 44 per cent of the respondents are opinion medium farmers and none of the respondents in the study areas seen to be large farmers.

SUGGESTIONS

The data analysis and interpretation of the problems, give the suggestion as follows:

- Government should provide quality seeds at low cost to the farmers.
- Government should give subsidies to the paddy cultivators.
- Providing fertilizers to the farmers on time.
- Much care should be taken by farmers to increase the quality of paddy.
- Create awareness among the farmers about the new techniques of paddy cultivation.
- Growers should assemble their produce in one place and processing and grading should be carried out collectively to earn better return for their produce.
- Give suggestions to the farmers about the soil erosion.

CONCLUSION

It may be said paddy cultivation is the most important and extensively grown food crop in the world paddy is one of the food crops produced and consumed in India, as well in Karnataka. Paddy cultivation is a preliminary attempt was made to interview people about their problems of paddy cultivation is heavy rains fall, shortage fertilizer, pest and diseases, high cost of production these problems can be overcome by government should give subsidies to the farmers.

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